

Membrane potential based assay for SLC6A5 using HEK-293 SLC6A5 OE cells

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Assay description

FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC6A5. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1).

SLC6A5 is a transporter protein of the SLC6 family of sodium- and chloride-dependent neurotransmitter transporters. It regulates synaptic glycine concentrations.

Glycine transport by SLC6A5 is coupled to the electrochemical movement of three Na⁺, favoring the maintenance of a high glycine concentration gradient along the presynaptic membrane.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC6A5 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced and mock control in parallel).

Membrane Potential assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 30 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of FMP-Blue-Dye (1X dye dissolved in Standard Tyrode's Buffer as indicated in the manufacturer manual) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λ_{exc} 510 - 545nm / λ_{em} 565 - 625 nm filter.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of substrate Glycine (2X in Standard Tyrode's buffer), starting from 3 mM, semi-log dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) were online injected at the plate reader and fluorescence recorded.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response (ΔF/F₀) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC₅₀/IC₅₀ values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC6A5
Synonyms	Glycine Transporter-2, GlyT2
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 6 (Neurotransmitter Transporter)
UniProt ID	Q9Y345
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE04Z9-5 (HEK-SLC6A5-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	Glycine
	PubChem CID	750
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Merck Millipore, # 104201
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 128 μM

Discussion

The Membrane Potential Assay for SLC6A5 showed a specific and dose-dependent fluorescent signal increase upon injection of Glycine. The increase in the fluorescence intensity is a result of cell depolarization that reflects the co-transport of Na⁺ through the transporter together with the substrates.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).